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Changing techniques of flint knapping in Chalcolithic times as an indicator of changes in the economy

In our view, the end of microlithic technology was associated not only with farming, but with a change in the entire economical system, where hunting is replaced by another type of economic activity. We consider this process on the example of a cultural community of Cucuteni-Trypillia.

Key words: *microlith, biface, Precucuteni, Cucuteni-Trypillia, flint knapping, Chalcolithic, Copper Age*

It is known that at the end of the Neolithic and early Chalcolithic in population of some cultures in the southeast Europe starts using large flint blades instead of microblades, along with the usage of triangular bifacial arrowheads and spears instead of inserts as geometric microliths. According to D.Yu. Nuzhnyi, the microlithic technology of Neo-Chalcolithic cultures is undergoing the final stage in the development of microlithic morphology. This was reflected in the unification of the types of microinventory, in the increase of the width of the blades, in the improvement of the technique of knapping and flat retouching. All this, gave impetus to the decline of microlithic technology (Nuzhnyi 2008, p. 185).

The purpose of the article is to elucidate the reason why such changes occur based on the example of the Cucuteni-Trypillia community. This process is well illustrated in this cultural complex on the border of the early and middle stages of the existence of community (Precucuteni-Cucuteni A/Trypillia A-Trypillia BI – 4900/4800 – 4300/4200 BC) (Rassamakin, 2012).

In the last decades, a lot of works have been written devoted to the issues of flint processing of these two periods (Shydlovskiy, Slesarev, 2015; Kiosak, Subbotin, 2016; Kiosak, 2016; Kiosak, 2016 a; Radomskiy, 2017; Vornicu, 2017; Crandell, Vornicu, 2015). The main technical and typological features of the early and middle-aged industries were established. So, to beginning with the existence of *Precucuteni-Trypillia culture characterized by the following signs:*

1. predominance of pencil-shaped, edge-faceted and conical single-platforms cores to obtain blades and bladelets (fig.1);
2. use mainly normal pressure to remove the regular blades;
3. production intended for bladelet (with width 0,8-1,2 cm) and blades (1,2-2,0 cm) (fig.2);

4. rhomboid microliths (less trapezoid) were used to equip the arrows (fig.3);

5. in the manufacture of microliths microburin technique was used;

6. the insert to agricultural tools was often used without secondary processing, in rare cases there is an irregular retouch or truncated (fig.3);

7. for products with secondary processing of ten flake blanks were chosen

8. mainly lateral retouching

The middle Trypillia complexes (period BI) are characterized by:

1. in the primary knapping the use of a technology of indirect percussion in the production of blades (as the main technique) (fig.4-5);

2. knapping is aimed at obtaining quite massive blade blanks – blades (with 1,2-2,0 cm width) and macroblades (2,0 cm and more);

3. the percentage of tools increases on blade blanks, and in some categories of inventory (like scrapers) blades are a major semi-finished product;

4. among the retouching blades are stand out on the basis of polished edges used for agricultural instrumentation (fig.6);

5. a significant percentage of cores due to make flakes;

6. the development of bifacial technology, which was aimed at obtain triangular weapons (fig.7);

7. starting to use parallel pressure retouching in the secondary knapping (with different percentages in the assemblages of sites).

At the same time, an increase in the width and the use of blades, mainly as the intermediary, is also traced in the end of the Precucuteni-Trypillia A (Kiosak 2016a; Shydlovskiy, Slesarev 2015; Kiosak, Subbotin 2016; Radomskiy 2017).

S.M. Bibikov and V.J. Sorokin both reasoned the reorientation of the production of large blades

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called the development of agriculture, which required the mass production of attachments to sickles (Bibikov 1953; Sorokin 1987). This, in turn, led to the refusal of the production of microlithic arrowheads. The same opinion was followed by A.V. Engovatova, who linked changes in tool making (or rather, in the working inventory) with changes in the way of farming (Engovatova 1993).

In our opinion, the reorientation to the production of macroblades became possible not only for agricultural development, but also through the separation of the «hunting» segment from this process, that is, through the change in the entire system of economy. With the development of flake bifacial technology in the Cucuteni-Trypillia, the production of microliths was stopped. The blade's direction of technology development ceased to be oriented on microinventory. Indeed, as D.Yu. Nuzhnyi rightly pointed, flint production in the previous ages depended on the parameters of microliths and this factor was important among the Stone Age industry. (Nuzhnyi 2008) Let us consider this question more in detail. The categories of inventory those are subject to change, which are directly related to agriculture and hunting, are inserts of sickles and equipment of the weapon. The materials from the settlements located on the Dniester River were used (Bernashivka I, Okopy, Luka-Vrublevetska – Precucuteni/Trypillia A; Ozaryntsi, Vasylivka, Ozheve-Ostriv, Hrynychuky, Polyvaniv Yar III – Cucuteni/Trypillia BI).

Sickles. By the end of the *early Trypillia*, the insert for an agricultural tool was more often used without secondary processing, in rare cases there was an extreme irregular retouch and truncated. Corner polishing indicated the use of ones in sickles of "Karanovo type" (Shydlovskiy, Slesarev 2015, p. 350). Sometimes researchers distinguish «harvest knives» (Semenov 1954, Larina 2013). For Bernashivka I, characteristic indentation widths range from 1.1-1.7 cm (data are based on the research results of the inventory in housing #8 and pits – only 26 items) (Shydlovskiy, Slesarev 2015, p. 350). Inserts from buildings #14-16, the same settlement, have similar metric indicators of width: from 1.1 up to 1.5 cm. However, four implements with a 2-2.2 cm width (only 15 items) were found. Among the materials of the Okopy settlement are 17 implements. Their width varies within 1.3-1.7 cm. Of these, 9 units made on blades 1.5-1.7 cm in width and in one case on a macroblade – 2,3 cm. Only three exemplars were corrected by lateral retouching. The largest collection of artifacts was discovered in the Luka-Vrublivetska settlement – 144 tools. According to publications, the width of the inserts did not exceed 2 cm. Special trassological researches are devoted to implements determining their use in "Karanovo type" sickles and in harvest knives (Bibikov 1962). So, the inserts of

the Early Trypillia time typologically do not differ among other inventory. Functional affiliation is determined at the macro level based on the presence of polishing. They were made by fragmentation of blades, occasionally correcting with a truncation and lateral retouching (Shydlovskiy, Slesarev 2015, p. 350).

The inserts of Trypillia BI has often been retouched and has the following metric indicators: Ozaryntsi (20 items) – the width of sixteen products varies within 1.5-2.0 cm (Radomskiy, Jakubenko 2016, p. 102-103), the other four are singular specimens from 2.1 to 3.1 cm; Polyvaniv Yar III (37 items) – inserts with a sharpening retouch from 1.5 to 1.7 cm, and with a transverse retouching – 1.5-2.0 cm (Popova 2003, p. 22-23); Ozheve-Ostriv (21 items) – 11 items from 1.3 to 2.0 cm and 10 items from 2.1 to 3.7 cm (five of which are 2.1 cm); Vasylivka – among the seven discovered, five specimens are in the range of 1.5-2.0 cm, two more have dimensions of 2.1 and 2.7 cm; Hrynychuky – 3 products fit in the limit of 1.5-2.0 cm, the other three have a width of 2.2-2.5 cm.

Thus, there is a certain imitation of Early Trypillia traditions, which manifests itself in the use of attachments up to 2 cm in width (with slight deviations). Taking into account that in the middle Trypillia assemblages mostly inserts without retouch (and only four of them in Ozheve-Ostriv and two in Ozaryntsi) have dimensions up to 2 cm, we can assume that some of their number was subjected to secondary processing not only for the purpose of exacerbating the working edge, but also to reduce the width of the preform.

Turning to the graphic of the ratio width and length of the inserts (not taken into account the process of recycling), there is a subsequent tendency in choosing blanks: the inserts, the width of which is less than 2 cm, were longer than the inserts, the width of which reaches 2 or more cm (graphic 1). The tendency to decrease the length is well illustrated in the graph with the exponential curve. Exception is the settlement of Vasylivka, where, on the contrary, their growth is traced.

Typically, the inserts of Trypillia BI period, as in the early period, does not differ from among other artifacts. Their functional attribute indicates only the polishing of the edges. There is no monotony of production: they were made by: «full» fragmentation of the blades (using only the medial part); «partial» fragmentation (separating only the distal part, or proximal). If the length of the blade satisfied, the whole half-finished product was used. Unity in the retouching is also absent: the exacerbating parallel, lateral, sometimes denticulate. It was applied to the cutting edge (in this case, the prevailing parallel, or denticulate retouching), and on the other side that was inserted into the frame, rarely retouched on both sides at once. The only

Graph. 1. The ratio of the width and length of contributions from the settlements of the period BI and their growth tendencies (by exponential).

admission in drowning, or more precisely, the alignment of the edge that was inserted into the product, is not followed. For example, in the settlement Horodnitsa-Horodyshe, the sharp edge was rounded off with the burin spall. In some cases abrupt retouching is found.

By the nature of polishing the edges, inserts are distinguished with angular and longitudinal polishing of the products. In our opinion, the inserts were put into the frame in such a way that one single blade of sickle was formed. An interesting finding was the insert made on the flake (from Ozheve-Ostriv). We hold the idea of using it on threshing boards (Skakun 2001).

In the chronological section, the inserts of the beginning of the stage of Cucuteni A-Trypillia BI are similar to the Early Trypillia metric indicators. Often, the required proportions were obtained due to do retouching that took out part of the blanks width. So, in our opinion, the «agricultural segment» was only one component that influenced the change of technological orientation in the production of blade semi-finished products.

Weapon. Equipped with Early Trypillian flint weapons are characterized by the use of geometric microliths (rhomboids or parallelograms) that were made in microburin technique (Shydlovskiy, Slesarev 2015, p. 352).

From the end of the early Trypillia, known triangular weapon is made by the method of bifacial processing, which fall into Early Trypillia settlement as individual products (“imports”) from the Balkan region. In this case, the production of microlith remains. Instead, from the first phase of the Trypillia BI stage, the microlithic technique, as well as the microliths (if the thesis is based on the fact that the microlith is an embedded hunting weapon made by combining the blunt-retouched surfaces with the sharp edge of the blades (Nuzhnyi 2008, p. 7, 20)), is replaced by triangular arrowheads, which gave impetus to the development of the second, flake line of the industry with bifacial processing.

At the specified time in the Cucuteni-Trypillia environment there are significant changes that are marked by migrations to the north and east, the increase in the number of fortified settlements, the spread of “battle axes” and the increase in the number of weapons (Dergachev 2007, p. 30-55; Klimscha 2011). The latter thesis can be rephrased due to the fact that in a number of early Trypillian settlements a small number of flint weapons were discovered due to imperfect research methods (instead of recent studies in Bernashivka I settlement (Shydlovskiy, Slesarev 2015)). In our opinion, one of the markers, which would indicate changes (cri-

sis), is not the number of weapons, but the change in its morphology, and, accordingly, the system of armament.

According to the study of the arrowheads of the Ozheve-Ostriv settlement, latter can be divided into three categories, depending on the type of weapon to be equipped: arrows, darts and spears (Chernovol, Radomskiy 2015). The first and second types of weapons existed in the Early Trypillian times as it was a light weapon. In the middle of the selected groups there are small deviations that can indicate the purpose of the tip (Chernovol, Radomskiy 2015). For example, some were used in hunting, others to protect or to assault. The isolation of the third group – spear, suggests that in the specified time they became a necessary component of the system of armament. The list at various times was used both as a weapon of flame (but in a lightweight version) and as a strike weapons. For example, when studying the stone industry of the Neanderthals, the researchers came to the conclusion about the usage of both spears, with the length of the knives, along with the tips of strike spears, reached 2.5 m (Schrenk, Müller 2005, p. 80-81). And in the XII-XV centuries AD the spear was an important barbed offensive weapon (of the first press). With the fact that some were used as a “sparrow battering ram” for dump, for example, a rider on a horse (Kirpichnikov, Medvedev 1985 p. 309-310; Voznyi, Phedoruk 2013 p. 53-54). Given that the number of fortified settlements increases at the BI stage, the use of the spear as offensive or “battering ram” seems to be quite feasible.

V.A. Dergachev conducted a comparison of the average data on the number of wild fauna populations in periods with a percentage ratio of the number of arrowheads (Dergachev 2007, p. 54-55). The results were as follows: the quantitative distribution of the weapons and the quantitative distribution of the wild paleofauna demonstrated two opposite trends. This is especially well seen at the level of the first two periods, when a sharp increase in the number of weapons on the transition from the Precucuteni-Trypillia stage A to the Cucuteni A-Trypillia BI is accompanied by a reduction in the number of bones of wild fauna. Accordingly, a new weapon (or its new equipment) is unlikely intending to improve hunting.

The refusal to produce microliths, in part, relates to a change in the weapon's system from

“hunting” to “offensive”. Reducing the “hunting segment” (which gave an important food product) in the system of the economy, involves filling this niche with other types of manage. V.F. Korobkova distinguishing economic variation notes that for some settlements, including the settlement of the period BI, livestock was either the main type of farming, or was at the same level with agriculture. Among such settlements the researcher names Polyvaniv Yar III, Berezivska HES, Sabatynivka (Trypillia BI) (Korobkova 1980: 212-213). In the economy of these settlements hunting played only an auxiliary role. Instead, on the settlement of Bernashivka, the hunting was dominant, and in the settlement of Luka-Vrublivetskaya hunting and livestock were on the same level (Korobkova 1980, p. 213-214). So, the change in the type of manage, from the earliest Trypillia to the beginning of Trypillia BI, was gradual.

Avoiding hunting, along with the cessation of the production of microliths and the transition to the production of bifaces, made it possible to “free” the blades technology from the microlithic proportions. The production of microblade completely ceases, and the number of bladelet in the stage of BI decreases to a negligible percentage.

The change in the technological direction of the production of blades of the early and middle Trypillia was the consequence of a change in the entire system of farming – the development of agriculture, the decline of hunting and obviously an increase in the role of livestock. All these processes were interconnected. The change in managing the economy began to manifest itself at the end of the early Trypillia (stage A/III-Precucuteni III). And although the production of microliths required smaller proportions of semi-finished products, but the width of the blade-blanks began to increase. At the next stage (BI), due to various reasons (mainly due to the tension in the environment not only of Cucuteni-Trypillia communities, but also among the Balkan cultures in general), the process of transition from one technique to another accelerated and became barely noticeable (at least in the area of the Dniester river).

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Зміни у технології кременеобробки за доби енеоліту як показник змін у економіці

За доби енеоліту в багатьох культурах відбувається переорієнтація крем'яного виробництва. Продукування мікролітів, якими оснащувалась дистанційна зброя, припиняється. Натомість, ширина платівчастих заготовок збільшується, а сам мікроліт замінюється трикутними вістрями, що виготовлялись за допомогою біфасіального розщеплення. Причиною переорієнтації на виробництво пластин та макропластин називають розвиток землеробства, що потребувало масове виготовлення вкладнів до серпів та жнивварських ножів, що і призвело до відмови виробництва мікролітичних наконечників стріл. На нашу думку, переорієнтація на продукування макропластин стало можливим не тільки внаслідок розвитку землеробства, а й через виокремлення «мисливського» сегменту з цього процесу, тобто через зміну всієї системи господарства. Такі зміни прослідковуються і у Трипільсько-Кукутеньському середовищі на межі раннього (A) та середнього (BI) етапів розвитку культури.

В роботі розглядаються зміни, що торкнулись таких категорій інвентарю як: 1) вкладнів серпів; 2) зброї. На основі проведеного аналізу висунуто припущення про те, що зміна у технологічній направленості виробництва платівок раннього та середнього Трипілля, стало наслідком зміни всієї системи господарства – розвиток землеробства, занепад мисливства та інтенсифікація скотарства. Всі ці процеси були взаємопов'язаними. Зміна у веденні господарства стала проявлятися ще у кінці раннього Трипілля (період A/III-Прекукутені III). На наступному ж етапі (BI), в силу різних причин (головно через напругу в середовищі не тільки трипільсько-кукутеньських спільностей, але і серед балканських культур вцілому) процес переходу від однієї техніки до іншої прискорився і став ледь помітним, а господарська діяльність змінилась, надавши пріоритет не тільки землеробству, а й скотарству, яке витісняє мисливський сегмент господарювання.

Ключові слова: *мікроліти, біфаси, Прекукутені, Кукутені-Трипілля, розщеплення кременю, енеоліт, мідно-кам'яна доба*

Fig. 1. Precucuteni-Trypillia A. Cores. 1-2 – Luka-Vrublevetskaya; 3-4 – Korman; 5-6 – Okopy.

Fig. 2. Precucuteni-Trypilla A. Tools. Luka-Vrublevetska.

Fig. 3. Precucuteni-Trypillia A. Microliths and insertions for agricultural tools. 1-8 – Okopy; 9-15 – Luka-Vrublevetskaya (9-15 – by S. Bibikov, 1953).

Fig. 4. Cucuteni-Trypillia Bl. Cores. Ozaryntsi.

Fig. 5. Cucuteni-Trypillia Bl. Cores. Ozheve-Ostriv.

Fig. 6. Cucuteni-Trypillia Bl. Insertions for agricultural tools. 1-3 – Ozaryntsi; 4-6 – Vasylivka; 7-9 – Ozheve-Ostriv.

Fig. 7. Cucuteni-Trypillia Bl. Bifacial weapons. 1-5 – Ozheve-Ostriv; 6-11 – Vasylivka.